

Exploration of K-ion Intercalation in Iron-Based Mixed-Polyanion Material

Chinnasamy Murugesan*, Baskar Senthilkumar and Prabeer Barpanda

Faraday Materials Laboratory, Materials Research Centre, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, 560012, India

*Corresponding author: chinnasamy@mrc.iisc.ernet.in, Phone No: +91 9524745470

Abstract:

Li-ion battery (LIB) innovation has demonstrated predominance in powering portable electronics and electric vehicles, it remains questionable whether the limited resources for many of the metals in LIBs can satisfy the demands from the large-scale application in grid-level storage. This uncertainty has generated broad research interest into cost-effective alternatives. In this context, Na-ion batteries (NIBs) have been examined as a promising option because of the abundance of Na and the similar chemistries of Li system. However, there are two fundamental natural issues associated with NIB technology (i) the higher standard redox potential of Na/Na⁺ usually translates into a lower working voltage than Li⁺ and (ii) graphite, a conventional anode for LIBs, cannot reversibly intercalate Na ions, instead requiring the use of hard carbon anodes. Thus, K-ion batteries (KIBs) with abundant K resources may be preferable as the standard redox potential of K/K⁺ is lower than that of Na/Na⁺, and graphite can store and release K ions. Keeping these issues in mind, we have investigated K-ion intercalating properties of Iron-based mixed-polyanion Na₄Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇. The cathode material was prepared by solution combustion synthesis using ascorbic acid as reducing agent and fuel. It has a 3D intercalating structure and the K-ion cell with Na₄Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇ cathode showed first discharge capacity of 118 mAh g⁻¹ (92 % of its theoretical capacity) and excellent capacity retention with good cycling stability (100 cycles). The work demonstrates the capability of the material as a high-performance cathode for K-ion batteries due to its multiple K-ion sites in the structure.

Keywords: mixed-polyanion cathode, Na₄Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇, solution combustion synthesis, potassium-ion battery, Capacity

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